

Interplay of Birth Order and Type of Course in Shaping Resilience and Efficacy among college Students

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Well-being in education extends beyond academic performance to include psychological strengths that help students navigate challenges. Resilience and efficacy are key components of psychological and cultural well-being, enabling effective coping with academic, social, and personal demands. The present study seeks to investigate the role of birth order and type of course in shaping students' resilience and efficacy level, within the framework of a cultural well-being perspective. Using stratified random sampling, 180 college students from three districts (Almora, Pithoragarh, & Bageshwar) of the Kumaon division of Uttarakhand were selected. Birth order was categorized into first-born, middle-born and last-born groups, with 60 students in each category. Within each group, 30 students from professional and non-professional courses were randomly selected using the personal data schedule. Efficacy and resilience level were assessed using the Psychological Capital Scale (Rani & Chaudhary, 2018). The results indicate that among groups formed based on birth order and type of course, differ significantly on the levels of efficacy and resilience. With respect to birth order, no significant difference was found in efficacy level at 0.05. However, a statistically significant difference was observed in resilience level. Similarly, students from different types of courses did not differ significantly in efficacy and resilience level. Moreover, the interaction between birth order and type of course was statistically significant for efficacy level, whereas non-significant difference for resilience level.

Keywords: Birth order, professional courses, non-professional courses, efficacy, resilience

The well-being of college students is influenced by a variety of personal, familial, and educational factors. The college period represents an important stage of transition in which students face academic demands, social expectations, and future-related concerns that require effective psychological adjustment. Their ability to manage these challenges often depends on the development of positive psychological strengths within the wider context of family and education (Bronfenbrenner, 1979; Triandis, 1995). In this manner, the behavior of students and adjustment may be understood better when examined through both influences of family and institution.

Within the family environment, birth order is considered an important variable that may influence personality development, responsibility, interpersonal roles, and coping patterns. Birth order can shape children's experiences and influence their psychological development (Adler, 1928). In Indian societies where family roles and relational structures are highly valued, birth order may therefore serve as a relevant factor in understanding individual differences among students (Kagitcibasi, 2007; Triandis, 1995). According to Luthans et al. (2007), student success depends not only on academic achievement but also on psychological resources such as resilience

and self-efficacy, which help students adapt and grow amid varying family dynamics and academic demands.

Students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses often face differing academic structures, expectations of performance, and career orientations, which may shape their learning experiences and adjustment patterns. Such educational differences may influence important psychological strengths such as resilience and efficacy. Resilience refers to the capacity to adapt positively and recover from adversity, whereas efficacy reflects an individual's belief in his or her ability to organize and perform actions necessary to achieve desired outcomes (Masten, 2014; Bandura, 1997).

The need for the present study arises from the limited attention given to the combined role of birth order and type of course in shaping resilience and efficacy among college students, particularly within the Indian socio-cultural context. The study is significant because it may contribute to a better understanding of how familial position and educational environment together influence students' psychological strengths and adjustment. The findings may further prove useful for teachers, counselors, parents, and educational institutions in developing supportive strategies for promoting student well-being. Birth order, whether as a first-born, middle child or youngest, shapes personality traits and coping styles through differential parental expectations and sibling interactions, influencing how students build resilience, or the adaptive capacity to bounce back from adversity (Masten, 2014).

An understudied familial element, i.e., birth order, shapes responsibility patterns, parental expectations, autonomy, and social roles (Adler, 1928; Sulloway, 1996). Professional courses often focus on structured training, performance evaluation, competitiveness, and future career readiness. Whereas a general degree course may provide the student with greater flexibility,

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theoretical orientation, and freedom. These differences in academic demands, expectations, and social valuation can influence the stress levels of students, their confidence, and psychological adaptation. Therefore, the type of education may function as an important determinant of resilience and efficacy.

As growing research on resilience and efficacy among students, a moderate amount of attention has been given to the combined influence of birth order and the type of course. Understanding how birth order positioning and the context of education interact can provide deeper insights into the psychological strengths and vulnerabilities of students. Such an approach perceives well-being as a multidimensional construct made by cultural norms, family systems, and institutional structures rather than individual traits.

The present study aims to examine birth order and type of course as determinants of resilience and efficacy among students, grounded in a cultural well-being perspective. The objectives of the study were following: to assess the level of resilience and efficacy among college students; to compare the groups formed based on birth order and type of courses on the level of resilience and efficacy among college students, to compare first born, middle born, and last born on the level of resilience and efficacy among students, to compare students of professional and non-professional courses on the level of resilience and efficacy among students and lastly to examine the interaction effect of birth order and type of courses for the level of resilience and efficacy among students.

Hypotheses of the Study

- Groups formed on the basis of birth order and type of courses would differ significantly in the level of resilience and efficacy.
- Firstborn, middle-born and last-born college students would differ significantly on the level of resilience and efficacy.
- Students of professional and non-professional courses would differ significantly in the level of resilience and efficacy.
- Birth order and type of courses would interact significantly for the variables resilience and efficacy level.

Method

Participants

The present study involved the selection of 180 college students through a stratified random sampling method. Initially, three districts of the Kumaon division of Uttarakhand, namely Almora, Pithoragarh, and Bageshwar were randomly selected. Students were drawn from colleges located within urban local bodies (Municipal areas such as Municipal Councils) of these districts. The participants were further classified on the basis of their birth order. Three birth order groups were formed first-born, middle-born and last-born, with 60 students in each group. Within each birth order group, 30 students were enrolled in professional courses and 30 students were enrolled in non-professional courses were randomly selected according to the personal data schedule.

Inclusion Criteria

- Individuals who are willing to give their consent.
- Mentally and physically healthy individuals were included.
- The students age ranging from 18 to 25 years were included in the study.
- Participants living with their intact family were included.

Exclusion Criteria

- Participants who did not provide their informed consent for the study.
- Individuals with any known major physical or mental illnesses or disabilities were excluded.
- Individuals below 18 and above 25 years of age range were excluded.
- Hostlers or subjects living away from their families were excluded.
- Those residing in joint families and single-parent families were excluded.

Research Design

In the current study, the researcher used a 3x2 factorial design to investigate the efficacy and resilience level in different groups.

Measures

Personal Data Schedule (PDS): It was a self-developed tool for gathering preliminary information about the subjects, including age, gender, birth order and type of courses.

Psychological Capital: This scale developed by Rani and Chaudhary (2018) was used to measure psychological capital among the participants. This scale is applicable for use on senior secondary and college students. It contains 34 items and 4 dimensions, namely hope, efficacy, resilience and optimism. The test retest reliability was 0.34 and split-half reliability was 0.64. The correlation coefficient between the dimensions of PCAS ranged from 0.28 to 0.41. So, the highly significant correlation shows that the subscales have high validity.

Procedure

Initially, college students were selected using a stratified random sampling technique. Subsequently, a personal data schedule administered by the researcher was used to classify and select students on the basis of their birth order and the type of course in which they were enrolled. This procedure ensured that the participants met the criteria specified in the research design. Following the selection of participants, the data were analyzed using a two-way analysis of variance.

Statistical Analysis

The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation, are used to study the nature of the variables. To ensure the normality of the data, skewness and kurtosis values were analyzed. To compare the different group Analysis of Variance and post-hoc statistical test was employed.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

		Professional courses		Non professional courses	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Efficacy	First born	33.06	4.53	29.26	6.18
	Middle born	28.73	5.07	30.70	4.92
	Last born	30.03	6.60	31.20	6.16
Resilience	First born	34.83	9.06	36.10	5.23
	Middle born	30.80	4.90	32.93	5.51
	Last born	35.26	5.48	33.93	7.79

Table 2
ANOVA on Efficacy

	Degree of Freedom (df)	Sum of squares (SS)	Mean squares (MS)	F ratio	Level of Significance at .05	Partial Eta Squared
Among Group	5	442.36	88.47	2.89	Sig	.07
Birth Order(A)	2	86.07	43.03	1.40	NS	.01
Type of Course (B)	1	86.80	86.80	2.83	NS	.01
Birth Order * Type of Course (A*B)	2	269.47	134.73	4.40	Sig	.04
Error	174	5319.83	30.57			

Note. Level of Significance at .05

Table 3
Mean of Six Groups on Efficacy

Birth Order / Type of Courses	B ₁ (Professional Courses)	B ₂ (Non-Professional Courses)	Total
	A ₁ (First Born)	33.06	29.26
A ₂ (Middle Born)	28.73	30.70	29.71
A ₃ (Last Born)	32.36	30.03	31.20
Total	31.38	30.00	30.69

Table 4
Critical Mean Difference 5% Level on Efficacy

Group	N	Standard Error of Difference	Critical Mean Difference
A/B	30	1.35	2.67

Table 5
ANOVA on Resilience

	Degree of Freedom (df)	Sum of squares (SS)	Mean squares (MS)	F ratio	Level of Significance at .05	Partial Eta Squared
Among Group	5	542.64	108.52	2.55	Sig	.06
Birth Order(A)	2	423.64	211.82	4.98	Sig	.05
Type of Course (B)	1	21.35	21.35	.50	NS	.00
Birth Order * Type of Course (A*B)	2	97.64	48.82	1.14	NS	.01
Error	174	7393.26	42.49			

Table 6
Mean of Four Groups on Resilience

Birth Order / Type of Courses	B ₁ (Professional Courses)	B ₂ (Non-Professional Courses)	Total
	A ₁ (First Born)	34.83	36.10
A ₂ (Middle Born)	30.80	32.93	31.86
A ₃ (Last Born)	35.26	33.93	34.60
Total	33.63	34.32	33.97

Table 7
Critical Mean Difference at 5% Level on Resilience

Group	N	Standard Error of Difference	Critical Mean Difference
A, B	30	1.59	3.14
A	60	1.16	2.30

Table 2 indicates that groups categorized on the basis of birth order and type of course differed significantly on efficacy level with the partial eta squared value 0.07, indicating a moderate effect size. Further from table 3, significant differences were revealed between A₁B₁ and A₁B₂; A₁B₁ and A₂B₁; A₃B₁ and A₂B₁. The rest of the groups revealed non-significant differences. Thus, the hypothesis was partially accepted.

Table 2 shows that groups formed solely on the basis of birth order did not differ significantly in the level of efficacy, leading to the rejection of the related hypothesis. Additionally, students enrolled in professional and non-professional courses did not differ significantly on the level of efficacy; hence, the related hypothesis was rejected.

Table 2 also illustrates a significant interaction effect between birth order and type of course for efficacy level, resulting in the acceptance of related Hypothesis. Furthermore, the partial eta squared value for the interaction effect was .048, suggesting a small to approaching moderate effect size.

From Table 5, it is evident that groups formed on the basis of birth order and type of course differed significantly in resilience level; therefore, Hypothesis 1 was partially accepted. Moreover, the partial eta squared value of .06 indicates a moderate effect size. Table 6 demonstrates that the significant differences were revealed between A₁B₁ and A₂B₁; A₂B₁ and A₃B₁, A₁B₂, and A₂B₂ groups. The rest of the groups revealed non-significant differences. Thus, the hypothesis was partially accepted.

Further, Table 5 shows that groups formed on the basis of birth order differed significantly in the level of resilience. As presented in Table 6, the firstborn had the highest resilience level and it significantly differed from middle-born students and was statistically similar to last-born students. Additionally, middle-born students also significantly differ from last-born. The partial eta squared value of .05 reflects a small effect size. Hence, acceptance of the related Hypothesis.

Table 5 also reveals that students enrolled in professional and non-

professional courses did not differ significantly on their levels of resilience, leading to the rejection of the related hypothesis. Additionally, the interaction effect between birth order and type of course for the level of resilience was found to be non-significant; therefore, rejection of the related hypothesis with a partial eta squared value of .04.

Discussion

The significant differences in efficacy across groups categorized by birth order and course type indicate that position of birth order and academic environment interact to shape beliefs of students' in their capabilities. Last-born students in professional courses attained the highest efficacy scores, the reasons may include parental guidance as it may shaped through first-borns' earlier experiences combined with emotional support provide them with adaptability for demanding tasks such as internships, team projects, and tight deadlines, reflecting Bandura's sources of mastery and social persuasion (Sulloway, 1996).

In contrast, first-born students in non-professional courses demonstrated the lowest scores. The reasons may be that their preference for structure and responsibility conflicts with flexible schedules and ambiguous assignments, which may result in reduced confidence and self-doubt when managing routine and academic challenges (Salmon & Daly, 1998).

No Significant difference in efficacy across birth-order groups suggests that in family settings, parental investment, educational support and expectations are often distributed relatively equally among siblings. Aligning with the study, Sharma and Singh (2022) have also reported no significant difference in birth order on efficacy level. Other reasons like Experiences that shape efficacy such as academic encouragement, peer comparison, and mastery experiences may be shared across birth-order positions.

The absence of significant differences in efficacy across professional and non-professional courses students shows that beliefs in their capabilities may be affected by sharing educational and psychosocial experiences. Although contemporary higher education aligned with frameworks like India's NEP 2020 emphasizes outcome-based learning, continuous internal assessments, collaborative projects, and skill-oriented pedagogy across disciplines (Government of India, 2020). It provides opportunities for mastery experiences, constructive feedback, and peer learning, which have been identified as major sources of self-efficacy, with mastery experiences being the most potent (Bandura, 1977). Moreover, as generalized self-efficacy reflects a broad, trait-like sense of competence rather than domain-specific confidence, structural differences in courses exert minimal influence when assessed globally, consistent with Bandura's mechanisms.

The significant differences in resilience level among groups formed by birth order and type of course with last-born students in professional courses showing the highest levels of resilience and middle-born students the lowest. The higher resilience level of last-born students in professional courses is likely due to greater parental support and adaptability (Sulloway, 1996). This, combined with strong academic demands, strengthens the coping (Connor & Davidson, 2003). Middle-born students, facing divided attention and role ambiguity at home, develop weaker coping resources, resulting in lower resilience levels across different course types (Salmon & Daly, 1998). Professional courses, with frequent evaluations,

projects, and internships, allow last-born students to apply and enhance their coping skills. In contrast, middle-born students receive less targeted support both at home and in academic settings, which may leave them more vulnerable to stress. This pattern demonstrates how the interaction of birth order and course type shapes resilience level in young adults.

The findings indicate that groups formed on the basis of birth order differed significantly in resilience level, with first-born students exhibiting higher levels of resilience than middle-born and last-born students. The reasons of this pattern may be understood in different ways. First-born children have greater parental expectations and responsibility from an early age, which encourages independence in them, self-regulation, and effective coping strategies. Such early responsibilities may strengthen problem-solving abilities and emotional control, thereby enhancing resilience level. Support for this explanation is provided by research demonstrating that resilience varies significantly across birth-order groups, highlighting the influence of family structure on adaptive functioning (Fukuya et al., 2021). In addition, differences in perceived parenting styles across birth-order positions have been shown to shape psychological adjustment, which suggests that expectations from parents and responsibility contribute meaningfully to resilience development (Someya et al., 2000).

Findings indicated a statistically significant difference in resilience levels between students pursuing professional courses and those enrolled in non-professional courses. The resilience models proposed by Connor and Davidson (2003) suggests resilience as a dynamic capacity strengthened through continuous engagement with stress and challenge. This difference in results can be attributed to prolonged exposure to demanding academic conditions, including heavy workloads, frequent evaluations, and compulsory internships, which repeatedly require adaptive coping and perseverance. Ungar's (2011) ecological framework further explains this pattern by highlighting career-oriented pressures in professional education as key promotive factors that support resilience development that are comparatively less pronounced in non-professional academic settings. Evidence from Indian studies on medical and health-profession students similarly demonstrates that resilience acts as a critical protective resource, enabling students to manage high academic stress while maintaining psychological well-being and academic performance (Kumar & Nancy, 2011; Sood et al., 2012; Shukla & Rishi, 2020).

Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research

- The study was limited to a restricted sample and region; future studies may use larger and more diverse samples.
- Only resilience and self-efficacy were examined in this study future studies may include additional psychological variables.
- Future research may apply mixed methods.
- Birth order and course type were treated broadly; future studies may explore detailed family and academic contexts.

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